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AN OVERVIEW ON ANTI-RETROVIRAL DRUGS: A REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

AIDS is not a virus but a set of symptoms caused by the HIV virus. A person is said to have AIDS when their immune system is too weak to fight off infection, and they develop certain defining symptoms and illnesses. AIDS alters the immune system, making people much more vulnerable to infections and diseases. The development of effective drug delivery approaches for the treatment of AIDS and HIV infection is a global challenge. HIV is a lifelong condition and currently there is no cure, although many scientists are working to find one. However, with medical care, including treatment called antiretroviral therapy, it's possible to manage HIV and live with the virus for many years. Treatment of HIV started as monotherapy initially, and then multiple drugs in regimens were given where patients had to consume 11-16 tablets per day. Now the mainstay of the treatment is a single fixed dose combination of Tenofovir, Lamivudine and Efavirenz per day or Zidovudine, Lamivudine and Nevirapine twice daily. Toxicity, resistance and adherence still remain a crucial issue. We need long acting depot preparations which would be efficacious for prevention, treatment and have fewer side effects. AIDS and HIV infection have reached pandemic levels in many parts of the world. Due to the complexities of virus infection cycle and the targets for delivery of antiretroviral drugs, more efficient drug delivery systems are needed.

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INTRODUCTION

According to global report of UNAIDS 2010 on average 33 million people in the world are living with HIV [1-2]. Sub Saharan Africa shares the biggest burden of HIV in the world with 22.5 million people living with HIV. Second highest number of HIV is in our part of the world- South and South East Asia where the estimated number of people living with HIV is 4.1 million. Even with the available efforts, it is becoming difficult to tackle HIV in the high burden countries of Asia and Africa due to existing poverty, illiteracy and overall ignorance.

Acquired immunodeficiency syndrome (AIDS) [3-4] is a chronic, potentially life-threatening condition caused by the human immunodeficiency virus (HIV). By damaging your immune system, HIV interferes with your body's ability to fight the organisms that cause disease. Without medication, it may take years before HIV weakens your immune system to the point that you have AIDS.

There's no cure for HIV/AIDS, but there are medications that can dramatically slow the progression of the disease. These drugs have reduced AIDS deaths in many developed nations. This means someone living with HIV, who is not receiving treatment, will find it harder and harder to fight off infections and diseases. If HIV is left untreated, it may take up to 10 or 15 years for the immune system to be so severely damaged it can no longer defend itself at all. However, the speed HIV progresses will vary depending on age, health and background. AIDS is a syndrome caused by a virus called HIV.

HIV is a retrovirus that gradually attacks the immune system, which protects human body against illness. This virus multiplies in T-helper cell (CD4) and gradually depletes them. The two main types are HIV-1 and HIV-2. HIV-1 is the most common type found worldwide. However HIV-2 is found mainly in Western Africa, with some cases in India and Europe.

Treatment of HIV started as monotherapy initially, and then multiple drugs in regimens were given where patients had to consume 11-16 tablets per day. Now the mainstay of the treatment is a single fixed dose combination of Tenofovir, Lamivudine and Efavirenz per day or Zidovudine, Lamivudine and Nevirapine twice daily. Toxicity, resistance and adherence still remain a crucial issue. We need long acting depot preparations which would be efficacious for prevention, treatment and have fewer side effects. AIDS and HIV infection have reached pandemic levels in many parts of the world. Due to the complexities of virus infection cycle and the targets for delivery of antiretroviral drugs, more efficient drug delivery systems are needed.

The development of effective drug delivery approaches for the treatment of AIDS and HIV infection is a global challenge. The advent of multidrug, highly active antiretroviral therapy (HAART), have increased the life span of HIV-infected patients. HIV is a lifelong condition and currently there is no cure, although many scientists are working to find one. However, with medical care, including treatment called antiretroviral therapy, it's possible to manage HIV and live with the virus for many years. Without treatment, a person with HIV is likely to develop a serious condition called AIDS. At that point, the immune system is too weak to fight off other diseases and infections. Untreated, life expectancy with AIDS is about three years. With antiretroviral therapy, HIV can be well-controlled and life expectancy can be nearly the same as someone who has not contracted HIV.

A better knowledge of the biological processes involved in specific viral infections, including interaction with specific host factors, is required to develop efficient screening methods and to identify viable targets. A wealth of information derived from massive sequencing techniques applied to humans and pathogens will be probably helpful in this process. Drug efficacy, toxicity and cost are also issues that need to be considered in the development of future antiviral drugs.

Worldwide target for HIV/AIDS is 90-90-90. This is an ambitious treatment target to help end the AIDS epidemic. By 2020, it includes 90% of all people living with HIV will know their HIV status, 90% of all people with diagnosed HIV infection will receive sustained ARV therapy, and 90% of all people receiving ARV therapy will have viral suppression. So, to achieve this goal we need to have more bullets in the form of new drugs which are less toxic and are more efficacious. New drug development efforts always try to bring in more efficacious and less toxic molecules. However, no drug is perfect. There are limitations like availability of platforms for bigger clinical trials with significant number of participants to look for adverse effects of the drug.

Genetic variations in PK/PD owing to ethnicity are also not known in all the cases. The costs of these newer drugs when they would be approved by FDA are also unpredictable as lot of research effort and regulatory efforts have gone into it. Once available in the market, continuous uninterrupted supply of these drugs with affordable cost for patient or free of cost under National program also remain points of consideration. Another big issue is about the acceptability of the drug and adherence as per the prescribed dosages and times span by the patients.

Basic Facts about HIV

1. The earlier HIV is diagnosed; the sooner treatment can start – leading to better long term health. So regular testing for HIV is important.
2. HIV cannot be transmitted through sweat, saliva or urine.
3. Using male condoms or female condoms during sex is the best way to prevent HIV.
4. HIV is a sexually transmitted infection (STI).
5. If you inject drugs, always use a clean needle and syringe, and never share equipment.
6. If you are pregnant and living with HIV, the virus in your blood could pass into your baby's body, or after giving birth through breastfeeding.
7. Taking HIV treatment virtually eliminates this risk.

Baseline Laboratory Tests

The necessary baseline laboratory investigations are listed below, the choice depends on the requirements of patient and clinical judgment of the ART clinician.

1. CD4 cell count.
2. Complete Blood Count, Haemoglobin percent.
3. ALT/SGPT – If needed other LFT (Liver function test).
4. Serum Creatinine – If needed other Kidney function test (Urea, Electrolytes).
5. Chest X ray, Sputum for AFB.
6. Hepatitis B and Hepatitis C screening test (for current or past PWID).
7. Urine for pregnancy test (if indicated in female).
8. Urine for Routine & Microscopic examination; Urinalysis to assess proteinuria.
9. Blood Sugar level.
10. For women, cervical Pap smear or other method of cervical cancer screening.

Guideline for Initiation of Anti Retroviral Drugs

Different guidelines exist for the treatment of HIV/AIDS which mainly include Centre for Disease Control (CDC), World Health Organization (WHO), British HIV association (BHIVA), and HIV clinical guidelines programme, New York and World Health Organization (NACO), India. Though ART is recommended for all HIV-infected individuals in most of the guidelines, regardless of CD4 count, NACO India is yet to implement this policy. ART is also recommended for HIV-infected individuals to prevent HIV transmission. Patient education and counselling is very important before initiating ART to overcome the challenges with the improper use of ART and to maximize the benefits.

Current Situation

Currently, 16 antiretroviral drugs are approved for treatment of HIV infection. However, even the best currently available regimens pose challenges with regard to adherence, toxicity, antiviral activity, and resistance. New drug development thus confronts the need for improved convenience and tolerability, reduced toxicity, and improved activity against both wild-type and drug-resistant viruses. Other goals of drug development include improved drug penetration into viral reservoirs (eg: genital tract and central nervous system) and exploitation of additional viral targets with the aims of achieving additive or synergistic effects with drugs from existing classes, reducing or preventing viral resistance, and improving treatment options in cases of drug resistance.

Major Goals of Antiretroviral Drugs

1. Maximal and durable suppression of viral load.
2. Restoration and/or preservation of immunologic function.
3. Reduction of HIV-related morbidity and mortality.
4. Improvement of quality of life of HIV infected persons.
5. Prevention of Mother to Child Transmission (PMTCT).
6. Providing Post Exposure Prophylaxis (PEP).
7. Minimise adverse effects of the treatment.
8. Prevent onward transmission of HIV.

These goals are achieved by suppressing viral replication completely for as long as possible, by using well tolerated and sustainable treatment taken with good adherence. With prolonged viral suppression, the CD4+ lymphocyte count usually increases, which is accompanied by a restoration of pathogen-specific immune function. For most patients, this results in a dramatic reduction in the risk of HIV-associated morbidity and mortality. It is still unclear whether immune function ever returns to full normality. Long-term cohorts show that patients who adhere well to ART have a near-normal life expectancy.

CLASSIFICATION ANTIRETROVIRAL DRUG [5-14]

This classification does not represent all the ARV drugs described above, these are the drugs currently recommended by guideline development team for the use. Depending on the mechanism of action, ARVs are categorized into following classes:

1. Nucleoside and nucleotide analogs (NRTI).
 - A. Nucleoside reverse transcriptase inhibitors.
 - B. Nucleotide reverse transcriptase inhibitors.
2. Non-nucleoside reverse transcriptase inhibitors (NNRTIs).
3. Protease inhibitors (PIs).
4. Integrase inhibitors.
5. Fusion inhibitors.
6. Pharmacokinetic enhancers.

The role of the antiretroviral treatment for prevention of HIV transmission has also been demonstrated. This underlines the need of ensuring access to quality treatment for all people living with HIV. The development of current ART guidelines is based on two fundamental principles of HIV care- to provide standardized treatment regimens and to promote more than ninety-five percent adherences to the regimens. This will ensure effective antiretroviral therapy with minimal possibilities of resistance development to ARV, and reduce chances of further HIV transmission.

Nucleoside/Nucleotide Reverse Transcriptase Inhibitors

The first effective class of antiretroviral drugs was the Nucleoside analogues. These are structural analogues of nucleosides and mimic the DNA building blocks there by stopping the viral replication process. The resulting DNA is incomplete and cannot create new virus. Nucleotide analogues work in the same way as nucleosides. All nucleoside analogs have been associated with lactic acidosis as their common side effects. For the details of individual ARV of this class, refer the **Table 1**.

Table 1: List of Nucleoside/Nucleotide Reverse Transcriptase Inhibitors.

S.No	Generic Name	Dose	Adverse effects
1	Zidovudine (Mar 1997)	300 mg twice daily.	Anaemia, Neutropenia, Bone Marrow Suppression, Gastro Intestinal Intolerance, Headache, Insomnia, Myopathy, Skin and Nail Hyper Pigmentation.
2	Lamivudine (Nov 1995)	150 mg twice daily or 300mg once daily.	Headache, Diarrhoea, Nausea, Vomiting, Minimal Toxicity.
3	Tenofovir (Oct 2001)	300 mg once daily.	Asthenia, Headache, Diarrhoea, Nausea, Vomiting, Flatulence Renal Insufficiency.
4	Abacavir (Dec 1998)	300 mg twice daily or 600mg once daily.	Hypersensitivity Reaction, Fever, Rash, Fatigue, Nausea, Vomiting, Anorexia, Respiratory and Cardiac Problems.
5	Emtricitabine (July 2003)	200 mg once daily.	Diarrhoea, Headache, Nausea, Rash, Skin Discoloration, Hepato Toxicity or lactic acidosis.

Non-Nucleoside Reverse Transcriptase Inhibitors

Non-nucleoside reverse transcriptase inhibitors (NNRTIs) stop HIV production by binding onto reverse transcriptase and preventing the conversion of RNA into DNA. These are called "non-nucleoside" inhibitors because they are not nucleoside analogues and act by physically blocking the reverse transcriptase. For the details refer the **Table 2**.

Table 2: List of Non-Nucleoside Reverse Transcriptase Inhibitors.

S.No	Generic Name	Dose	Adverse effects
1	Nevirapine (Mar 2011)	200 mg once daily for 14 days followed by 200 mg twice daily.	Hepatitis, Hepatic Toxicity; Skin Rash, Stevens Johnson Syndrome.
2	Efavirenz (Sep 1998)	600 mg once daily.	CNS Symptoms, Insomnia, Confusion, Hallucinations, and Personality Change.
3	Rilpivirine (May 2011)	25mg once daily.	Blistering Skin, Redness or Swelling of Eyes, Insomnia, Confusion.

Protease Inhibitors

Protease inhibitors work at the last stage of the viral reproduction cycle. These drugs prevent HIV from being successfully assembled and released from the infected CD4 cell. For the details of individual ARV of this class refer the **Table 3**.

Table 3: List of Protease Inhibitors.

S.No	Generic Name	Dose	Adverse effects
1	Lopinavir (Sep 2000)	200mg Twice daily.	Diarrhoea, Nausea, Vomiting, Abnormal Lipid Profiles, Glucose Intolerance.
2	Saquinavir (Dec 1995)	1000mg Once daily.	Diarrhoea, Nausea, Vomiting, Headache, Photosensitivity.
3	Atazanavir (June 2003)	300mg Once daily.	Hyperbilirubinemia, Lipid Problem, Hyperglycaemia.
4	Darunavir (June 2006)	600mg or 800mg Twice daily.	Diarrhoea, Nausea, Vomiting, Headache, Abnormal Lipid Profiles, Skin Rash.
5	Ritonavir (Mar 1996)	50 mg Twice or 100mg Once daily.	Diarrhoea, Nausea, Vomiting, Abnormal Lipid Profiles, Glucose Intolerance.
6	Tipranavir (June 2005)	250mg Twice or 500mg Once daily.	Joint pain or Stiffness, Diarrhoea, Headache. Throat Tightness, Redness or Swelling of Eyes, Insomnia, Confusion.

Integrase Inhibitors

An enzyme found in HIV (and other retroviruses). HIV uses integrase to insert (integrate) its viral DNA into the DNA of the host CD4 cell. Integration is a crucial step in the HIV life cycle and is targeted by a class of antiretroviral (ARV) HIV drugs called integrase strand transfer inhibitors (INSTIs). By blocking integrase, integrase inhibitors prevent HIV from multiplying and can reduce the amount of HIV in the body, refer Table 4.

Table 4: List of Integrase Inhibitors.

S.No	Generic Name	Dose	Adverse effects
1	Raltegravir (Oct 2007)	400mg Twice daily	Diarrhoea, Nausea, Vomiting, Headache, Insomnia.
2	Dolutegravir (Aug 2013)	50mg Once or Twice daily	Diarrhoea, Nausea, Vomiting, Headache, Abnormal Lipid Profiles, Skin Rash.

Fusion Inhibitors

Entry inhibitors, also known as fusion inhibitors, are a class of antiretroviral drugs, used in combination therapy for the treatment of HIV infection. This class of drugs interferes with the binding, fusion and entry of the HIV virions to a human cell. By blocking this step in HIV's replication cycle, such agents slow the progression from HIV infection to AIDS, refer the Table 5.

Table 5: List of Fusion Inhibitors.

S.No	Generic Name	Dose	Adverse effects
1	Maraviroc (Aug 2007)	150mg Twice or 300mg Once daily.	Nausea, Upper Stomach Pain, Loss of Appetite, Dark Urine, Jaundice.
2	Enfuvirtide (Mar 2003)	90mg Twice daily.	Constipation, Diarrhoea, Rapid Heart Rate, Nausea, Abnormal Lipid Profiles, Skin Rash.

Pharmacokinetic Enhancers

A pharmacokinetic enhancer is used to boost the effectiveness of another drug. When the two drugs are given together, the pharmacokinetic enhancer interferes with the breakdown of the other drug, which allows the drug to remain in the body longer at a higher concentration. Pharmacokinetic enhancers are used in HIV treatment to increase the amount of other HIV medicines in the blood, refer the Table 6.

Table 6: List of Pharmacokinetic Enhancer.

S.No	Generic Name	Dose	Adverse effects
1	Cobisistat (Sep 2014)	150mg Once daily.	Nausea, Constipation, Diarrhoea, Loss of Appetite, Skin Rash.

MECHANISMS OF ACTION

To understand the mechanism of action of ARV, one needs to understand the basic steps of the viral replication, in other words life cycle of HIV virus. Virus enters into the CD4 (host) cell involving glycoprotein of the virus and receptors of host cells. The process is called fusion. ARVs interfering with the fusion are called fusion inhibitors. This is the new class of ARV and it includes the drugs like T 20 (Enfuvirtide), CCR5 entry inhibitors (Maraviroc) and CXCR4 antagonist.

After the fusion with the host cell membrane, viral particles including the viral RNA and the enzymes (reverse transcriptase, integrase and protease) enter into the cytoplasm of the host cell. The first process inside the host cell is the reverse transcription in which viral DNA is synthesized from viral RNA. The process involves the reverse transcriptase enzyme. The ARVs interfering with this process are called nucleoside and nucleotide reverse transcriptase inhibitors (NRTI) and non-nucleoside reverse transcriptase inhibitors (NNRTI). The viral DNA synthesized in cytoplasm travels to the nucleus of the host cell, where it integrates with the DNA of the host cell with the help of integrase. Integrase inhibitors are the ARVs that block the process of integration. After integration, the DNA of the infected cell converts into the viral DNA and starts to produce copies of viral RNA.

For the production of viral particles, the RNA copies thus produced need to be cut into particles of exact size with the help of protease. Protease inhibitors (PI) interrupt this process. The boosted PIs (combination of two types of PI) increase the effectiveness, stability of ARV and minimize the side effects. The viral RNA after the action of protease converts into the viral particles. These particles assemble with the enzymes into a capsule, which eventually leaves the infected cell by the process called budding. The viruses after budding develop into the mature viruses. There are some ARV inhibiting the process of maturation and are called maturation inhibitors. The following graphic represents the process viral replication and the action of the ARV in different stages of the replication as shown in Fig.1, Fig.2 and refer the Table 7.

Fig. 1: Targets of Antiretroviral Drugs in the HIV Life Cycle.

Fig. 2: Antiretroviral drugs approved for HIV infection.

Table 7: List of Fixed-dose combinations for antiretroviral drugs.

Brand	Drug Names	FDA Approval	Company
Combivir	Lamivudine + Zidovudine	26-9-1997	GlaxoSmithKline
Kaletra	Lopinavir + Ritonavir	15-9-2000	Abbott Laboratories
Trizivir	Abacavir + Lamivudine + Zidovudine	15-11-2000	GlaxoSmithKline
Epzicom, Kivexa	Abacavir + Lamivudine	2-8-2004	GlaxoSmithKline
Truvada	Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate + Emtricitabine	2-8-2004	Gilead Sciences
Atripla	Emtricitabine + Efavirenz + Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate	12-7-2006	Gilead Sciences, Bristol-Myers Squibb
Complera, Eviplera	Emtricitabine + Rilpivirine + Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate	10-8-2011	Gilead Sciences, Janssen Therapeutics
Stribild	Elvitegravir + Cobisistat + Emtricitabine + Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate	27-8-2012	Gilead Sciences
Triumeq	Abacavir + Dolutegravir + Lamivudine	22-8-2014	ViiV Healthcare
Evotaz	Atazanavir + Cobisistat	29-1-2015	Bristol-Myers Squibb
Prezcobix	Darunavir + Cobisistat	29-1-2015	Janssen Therapeutics
Dutrebis	Lamivudine + Raltegravir	6-2-2015	Merck & Co.
Genvoya	Elvitegravir + Cobisistat + Emtricitabine + Tenofovir Alafenamide Fumarate	5-11-2015	Gilead Sciences
Descovy	Tenofovir Alafenamide Fumarate + Emtricitabine	4-4- 2016	Gilead Sciences
Odefsey	Emtricitabine + Rilpivirine + Tenofovir Alafenamide	1-3-2016	Gilead Sciences
Juluca	Dolutegravir + Rilpivirine	21-11- 2017	ViiV Healthcare
Biktarvy	Bictegravir + Emtricitabine + Tenofovir Alafenamide Fumarate	21-2-2018	Gilead Sciences

CONCLUSION

New antiretroviral drugs are needed to improve convenience, tolerability, safety and antiviral activity of antiretroviral therapy. Promising agents are in development in existing classes and in new classes (HIV entry and HIV integrase inhibitors). Additional steps in the viral life cycle, including viral uncoating and viral assembly, and other enzymes can and should be targeted in future drug development. Additional approaches using immune therapies such as interleukin- 2 and therapeutic HIV vaccines may complement the use of current and future antiretroviral agents. As learnt from the HIV experience, monotherapy should be considered suboptimal therapies and combination therapies are expected to prevail in the future treatment of viral infections. Good combination therapies rely on the exploitation of multiple targets and/or mechanisms of action. Further basic and clinical research aimed at identifying and developing promising antiretroviral agents is needed.

Abbreviations

AIDS – Acquired Immunodeficiency Syndrome
 ARD – Anti-Retroviral Drugs
 HIV – Human Immunodeficiency Virus
 CDC – Centre for Disease Control
 WHO – World Health Organization

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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